

Studies on Surface Activity of Cellulose Nitrate/Lecithin-DPC Systems

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Manuscript received 22 August 1996, revised 18 February 1997, accepted 25 February 1997

Immobilization of surfactant systems, lecithin and dodecylpyridinium chloride (DPC) when used separately and in combination using cellulose nitrate microfilter as substrate, has been investigated. The results show immobilization to be diffusion-controlled. Estimation of interfacial excess has also been carried out on the basis of alteration in membrane resistance due to accumulation of surfactant molecules in the interfacial region.

Mixed surfactant systems are used preferentially in many applications of practical interest, because they exhibit somewhat enhanced surface activity^{1,2}. Surfactants endowed with structural similarity of their hydrophobic portions are used most often in such studies. It is also of interest to investigate systems made up of structurally dissimilar surfactants because such systems may also exhibit synergism. We have chosen to investigate interfacial surface activity of lecithin-DPC system by studying immobilization of these surfactants separately and in combination, using cellulose nitrate microfilter substrate. Lecithin is a surfactant of immense interest and biological significance³ while DPC is a well-characterized ionic surfactant.

Results and Discussion

Surface tension data show that the critical micelle concentration (CMC) of lecithin is $\sim 3 \times 10^{-4} M$ while that DPC is $\sim 5 \times 10^{-3} M$. The CMC of lecithin reduces to $\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ when used in combination with DPC. The CMC of DPC also reduces to $\sim 0.1 \times 10^{-4} M$ in the presence of lecithin. These data show that the mixed systems are endowed with somewhat enhanced surface activity. Such behaviour in mixed systems is attributed to the existence of intermolecular interactions^{1,4,5}.

Immobilization of surfactants is accompanied by increase in the resistance of the supporting substrate⁶. The immobilized structures are commonly called liquid membranes. The results (Figs. 1 and 2) show that resistance of the systems attains time invariant values which depend on the experimental conditions. Time needed for complete liquid membrane formation (t_s) presented in Tables 1 and 2, is seen to decrease with increase in surfactant concentration. Furthermore, when surfactants are used separately, the t_s values are larger than those for the mixed surfactant system, in spite of saturation resistance being relatively higher in the latter case. This also indicates that the mixed surfactant immobilized layer is formed more readily.

The extent of accumulation of surfactant molecules can be assessed in terms of $(R_s - R_0)$, where R_0 denotes the initial resistance and R_s the saturation resistance. The results (Figs. 3 and 4) show that $(R_s - R_0)$ increases with increas-

Fig. 1. Variation of membrane resistance with time when equilibrated with solutions of different concentrations of lecithin containing $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ DPC: (Δ) $0.50 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\circ) $0.75 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\square) $1.00 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\bullet) $1.25 \times 10^{-6} M$ and (\blacktriangle) $1.50 \times 10^{-6} M$.

TABLE 1—SURFACE EXCESS AND TIME NEEDED FOR COMPLETE LIQUID MEMBRANE FORMATION VALUES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF DODECYL PYRIDINIUM CHLORIDE

[DPC] $\times 10^{-6}$ M	$\Gamma \times 10^{-11}$ mol cm ⁻²	t_s s	In presence of lecithin $3.0 \times 10^{-4} M$	
			$\Gamma \times 10^{-10}$ mol cm ⁻²	t_s s
2.0	2.219	363	10.392	315
4.0	4.440	360	20.784	264
6.0	6.659	324	31.177	273
8.0	8.879	312	41.569	237
10.0	11.099	291	51.961	228

ing surfactant concentration in both the cases and tends to attain limiting value beyond certain concentration which corresponds to their CMC values determined by surface tension measurements. These observations are in conformity with the expectation that a completely formed immo-

Fig. 2. Variation of membrane resistance with time when equilibrated with solutions of different composition with respect to DPC containing $3 \times 10^{-4} M$ lecithin : (Δ) $2 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\circ) $4 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\square) $6 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\bullet) $8 \times 10^{-6} M$, (\blacktriangle) $10 \times 10^{-6} M$ and (\blacksquare) $12 \times 10^{-6} M$.

bilized layer of surfactant molecules in the interfacial region exists at concentrations beyond their CMC. When surfactants are used separately the value of $(R_s - R_0)$ is very small in comparison to that in the mixed surfactant system. This indicates that the mixed surfactant immobilized layer is more resistive compared to cumulative resistance obtained using resistance values when lecithin or DPC are used separately, using equation (1),

$$\text{Cumulative resistance} = [(R_{DPC} - R_0) + (R_L - R_0)] \quad (1)$$

This also indicates possibility of significant interactions amongst the surfactant molecules.

TABLE 2—SURFACE EXCESS AND TIME NEEDED FOR COMPLETE LIQUID MEMBRANE FORMATION VALUES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF LECITHIN

[Lecithin] $\times 10^{-6} M$	$\Gamma \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol cm}^{-2}$	t_s s	In presence of DPC $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$	
			$\Gamma \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol cm}^{-2}$	t_s s
0.50	1.794	426	4.036	306
0.75	2.691	348	6.054	279
1.00	3.587	327	8.072	273
1.25	4.484	300	10.089	261
1.50	5.381	261	12.108	246

Progress of immobilization is measured in terms of the rate of change of resistance with time under different experimental conditions. The value of $d(R_t - R_0)/dt$ is found

Fig. 3. Dependence of $(R_s - R_0)$ on composition : (\bullet) DPC, (\circ) (DPC + $3 \times 10^{-4} M$ lecithin) experimental values; (Δ) cumulative resistance for (DPC + $3 \times 10^{-4} M$ lecithin) estimated using equation (1).

Fig. 4. Dependence of $(R_s - R_0)$ on composition : (\bullet) lecithin, (\circ) (lecithin + $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ DPC) experimental values; (Δ) cumulative resistance of (lecithin + $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ DPC) estimated using equation (1).

to increases with surfactant concentration. In the case of mixed surfactant system, the quantity $d(R_t - R_0)/dt$ is larger in comparison to the individual surfactant systems. This indicates that in the case of mixed surfactant systems immobilization of surfactant molecules in the interfacial re-

gion occurs with relatively greater ease.

Immobilization can be visualised to involve attachment of surfactant molecules present in the immediate neighbourhood of the substrate and replenishment of the depletion layer thus formed by diffusional migration of the surfactant molecules. It may thus involve (i) attachment controlled immobilization, (ii) diffusion-controlled immobilization, or (iii) both (i) and (ii) may be involved. If (i) were true then $d(R_t - R_0)/dt$ should change with time. This is not found to be the case experimentally. If (ii) is true $d(R_t - R_0)/dt$ should not change with time. This is in conformity with the experimental results. Immobilization is thus faster step and the rate of immobilization is determined by diffusional migration of the surfactant molecules into the depletion layer. This is further substantiated by the linear plots of $d(R_t - R_0)/dt$ against surfactant concentration. According to Fick's first law of diffusion

$$J = -D \frac{dc}{dx} \quad (2)$$

may be considered to be a measure of diffusional migration, (J) so that

$$\frac{d(R_t - R_0)}{dt} = -D \frac{(C - C_0)}{\delta} \quad (3)$$

where, δ is the thickness of the depletion layer and C_0 the concentration of surfactant at the interface. If immobilization is diffusion-controlled, $C_0 \approx 0$. Thus

$$\frac{d(R_t - R_0)}{dt} = -D \frac{C}{\delta} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{d(R_t - R_0)}{dt} \propto C \quad (5)$$

as observed experimentally.

A quantitative measure of activity of a surfactant is surface excess defined as the excess concentration of surfactant molecules at the surface relative to the bulk phase of the solution. In the present case we define interfacial excess in an analogous manner to express accumulation of a surfactant in the substrate-solution interfacial region. Interfacial excess may be estimated using the Gibbs adsorption isotherm⁷ as

$$\Gamma = - \frac{C}{RT} \left(\frac{\delta R_c}{\delta C} \right)_T \quad (7)$$

where, R_c is the resistance of the composite system. The variation of interfacial excess with concentration when lecithin and DPC are used separately or in combination is presented in Tables 1 and 2. It is seen to increase with increase in concentration and tends to attain a maximum value as the concentration approaches CMC. Beyond CMC the interfacial region cannot accommodate the surfactant mole-

cules and its coverage is complete. The interfacial excess values are substantially greater in case of the mixed surfactant systems. This supports the inference that when mixed surfactant system is used, the immobilized interfacial layer has enhanced compactness because of the existence of intermolecular interactions between the surfactant molecules.

Experimental

Lecithin (L- α -phosphatidylcholine, purity 99.9%; Sigma) and DPC (purity 99.7%; Aldrich) were used as such. The aqueous solutions of lecithin, DPC and their mixtures were prepared as described earlier⁸. Lecithin was dissolved in ethanol and added to the aqueous phase with constant stirring to obtain solutions of desired concentration. In the aqueous solution thus prepared, the final concentration of ethanol never exceeded 1% by volume. Upto this concentration, no change in the surface tension could be detected in the absence of lecithin.

The surface tension was measured using a Tensiomat 21 (Fisher Scientific Instrument) instrument.

Cellulose nitrate microporous filter (Whatmann; dia. 0.5 cm, pore size 0.4 μm) was used as a substrate. Experimental setup used for resistance measurement has already been reported⁹. A piece of cellulose nitrate microporous filter was fixed in a glass cell and kept in contact with the surfactant solution of desired concentration containing 0.10 mol dm⁻³ NaCl solution. The resistance across the membrane was measured with the help of a digital multimeter (HIL 2161) using platinum electrodes.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.K.S.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Research Associateship. The authors acknowledge with thanks the facilities provided by Head, Chemistry Department, Gorakhpur University.

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